

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
SOCCER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

Date: 2023/03/21

INDEX

- 1. Abstract**
- 2. Tools used**
- 3. Languages**
 - PHP
 - HTML
 - CSS
 - BOOTSTRAP
 - MYSQL
- 4. Program**
 - Home.php
 - Connect.php
- 5. Screenshots**

ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION:

This web application comes with a simple interface where a person can simply login or register using some basic requirement. That login welcome's him to the main interface which held with some data fields. The main fields are Players, Store, Management, Sponsors, Events. The user can simply visit this fields and give support to his favourite team and if a person who is dreams to join with this team at any of the field can apply his request through this web application. The live updates about the team should be released through the event field in the web application.

OBJECTIVE:

The main aim of our project is to put a football team under the hand of common people. Which means a common man who has an active internet connection and a laptop or a smartphone can know the team updates, on time. If a person is highly passionate to join with this team in any of the job positions can simply apply through this web application. The team's official store is also available at this application so that purchasing of tickets, jersey's, badges etc. are very easy. whereabouts of the sponsors is also displays on the website this makes helpful to the sponsors.

MATERIALS:

'**SOCCER MANAGEMENT**' web-application is built in Html, CSS, Bootstrap as frontend and backend is integrated in PHP. MySQL is used as database to arrange all the data.

TOOLS USED

OPERATING SYSTEM:-WINDOWS 10

FRONT END:-HTML, CSS, BOOTSTRAP

BACK END:-PHP

DATABASE:- MYSQL

LANGUAGES

PHP

PHP is a general-purpose scripting language geared towards web development.[7] It was originally created by Danish-Canadian programmer Rasmus Lerdorf in 1994.[8] The PHP reference implementation is now produced by The PHP Group.[9] PHP originally stood for Personal Home Page,[8] but it now stands for the recursive initialism PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor.[10] PHP code is usually processed on a web server by a PHP interpreter implemented as a module, a daemon or as a Common Gateway Interface (CGI) executable. On a web server, the result of the interpreted and executed PHP code – which may be any type of data, such as generated HTML or binary image data – would form the whole or part of an HTTP response. Various web template systems, web content management systems, and web frameworks exist which can be employed to orchestrate or facilitate the generation of that response. Additionally, PHP can be used for many programming tasks outside the web context, such as standalone graphical applications[11] and robotic drone control.[12] PHP code can also be directly executed from the command line. The standard PHP interpreter, powered by the Zend Engine, is free software released under the PHP License. PHP has been widely ported and can be deployed on most web servers on a variety of operating systems and platforms.[13] The PHP language evolved without a written formal specification or standard until 2014, with the original implementation acting as the de facto standard which other implementations aimed to follow. Since 2014, work has gone on to create a formal PHP specification.[14] W3Techs reports that, as of January 2022, "PHP is used by 78.1% of all the websites whose server-side programming

language we know." [15] PHP version 7.4 is the most used version. Support for version 7.3 was dropped on 6 December 2021.

HTML

The **HyperText Markup Language** or **HTML** is the standard markup language for documents designed to be displayed in a web browser. It can be assisted by technologies such as Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and scripting languages such as JavaScript.

Web browsers receive HTML documents from a web server or from local storage and render the documents into multimedia web pages. HTML describes the structure of a web page semantically and originally included cues for the appearance of the document.

HTML elements are the building blocks of HTML pages. With HTML constructs, images and other objects such as interactive forms may be embedded into the rendered page. HTML provides a means to create structured documents by denoting structural semantics for text such as headings, paragraphs, lists, links, quotes and other items. HTML elements are delineated by *tags*, written using angle brackets. Tags such as `` and `<input />` directly introduce content into the page. Other tags such as `<p>` surround and provide information about document text and may include other tags as sub-elements. Browsers do not display the HTML tags but use them to interpret the content of the page.

HTML can embed programs written in a scripting language such as JavaScript, which affects the behavior and content of web pages. Inclusion of CSS defines the look and layout of content. The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), former maintainer of the HTML and current maintainer of the CSS standards, has encouraged the use of CSS over explicit presentational HTML since 1997.^[2] A form of HTML, known as HTML5, is used to display video and audio, primarily using the `<canvas>` element, in collaboration with java script.

CSS

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is a style sheet language used for describing the presentation of a document written in a markup language such as HTML.^[1] CSS is a cornerstone technology of the World Wide Web, alongside HTML and JavaScript.^[2]

CSS is designed to enable the separation of presentation and content, including layout, colors, and fonts.^[3] This separation can improve content accessibility; provide more flexibility and control in the specification of presentation characteristics; enable multiple web pages to share formatting by specifying the relevant CSS in a separate .css file, which reduces complexity and repetition in the structural content; and enable the .css file to be cached to improve the page load speed between the pages that share the file and its formatting.

Separation of formatting and content also makes it feasible to present the same markup page in different styles for different rendering methods, such as on-screen, in print, by voice (via speech-

based browser or screen reader), and on Braille-based tactile devices. CSS also has rules for alternate formatting if the content is accessed on a mobile device.^[4]

The name *cascading* comes from the specified priority scheme to determine which style rule applies if more than one rule matches a particular element. This cascading priority scheme is predictable.

BOOTSTRAP

Bootstrap is a free and open-source CSS framework directed at responsive, mobile-first front-end web development. It contains HTML, CSS and (optionally) JavaScript-based design templates for typography, forms, buttons, navigation, and other interface components.

MYSQL

- **MySQL** is an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS) Its name is a combination of "My", the name of co-founder Michael Widenius's daughter,^[7] and "SQL", the abbreviation for Structured Query Language. A relational database organizes data into one or more data tables in which data types may be related to each other; these relations help structure the data. SQL is a language programmers use to create, modify and extract data from the relational database, as well as control user access to the database. In addition to relational databases and SQL, an RDBMS like MySQL works with an operating system to implement a relational database in a computer's storage system, manages users, allows for network access and facilitates testing database integrity and creation of backups.
- MySQL is free and open-source software under the terms of the GNU General Public License, and is also available under a variety of proprietary licenses. MySQL was owned and sponsored by the Swedish company MySQL AB, which was bought by Sun Microsystems (now Oracle Corporation). In 2010, when Oracle acquired Sun, Widenius forked the open-source MySQL project to create MariaDB
- MySQL has stand-alone clients that allow users to interact directly with a MySQL database using SQL, but more often, MySQL is used with other programs to implement applications that need relational database capability. MySQL is a component of the LAMP web application software stack (and others), which is an acronym for *Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl/PHP/Python*. MySQL is used by many database-driven web applications, including Drupal, Joomla, phpBB, and WordPress. MySQL is also used by many popular websites, including Facebook, Flickr, MediaWiki, Twitter, and YouTube

PROGRAM

HOME.PHP

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta http-equiv="X-UA-Compatible" content="IE=edge">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0">
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="style.css">
  <!-- JavaScript Bundle with Popper -->
  <script src="https://cdn.jsdelivr.net/npm/bootstrap@5.1.3/dist/js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"
  integrity="sha384-
  ka7Sk0Gln4gmtz2MIQnikT1wXgYsOg+OMhuP+IIRH9sENBO0LRn5q+8nbTov4+1p"
  crossorigin="anonymous"></script>
  <!-- CSS only -->
  <link href="https://cdn.jsdelivr.net/npm/bootstrap@5.1.3/dist/css/bootstrap.min.css"
  rel="stylesheet" integrity="sha384-
  1BmE4kWBq78iYhFIdvKuhfTAU6auU8tT94WrHftjDbrCEXSU1oBoqyl2QvZ6jIW3"
  crossorigin="anonymous">
  <title>SOCCER MANAGEMENT</title>
</head>
<body>
<section id="header-sections">
<header>
  <nav class="navbar">
```

```

<div class="container-fluid">
  <div>
    <a href="#" style="text-decoration: none;
    font-weight: 700; font-size: 25px;">
      SOCCER MANAGEMENT
    </a>
  </div>
  <div class="nav navbar-nav1">
    <a href="home.php" class="btn text-light">Home</a>
    <a href="registration.php" class="btn text-light">Registration</a>
    <a href="purchase.php" class="btn text-light">Purchase</a>
    <a href="tickets.php" class="btn text-light">Tickets</a>
    <a href="appointment.php" class="btn text-light">Appointment</a>
    <a href="event.php" class="btn text-light">Events</a>
    <a href="admin.php"> <button type="button" class="btn btn-primary text-
light"><b>ADMIN</b></button></a>
  </div>
</div>
</nav>
</header>
</section>
<section id="slpor">
  
</section>
<section>
<section class="about my-5">
  <div class="container">
    <h3 style="color:
#323049;text-align: center;"><u><b>VISION</b></u></h3>

```

<p style="line-height: 2.0;color:

#323049;font-size: 20px;"> Vision is not only about how well you can see, it also involves 17 different visual skills that enable accurate, smooth, and precise eye movements for clear and comfortable vision— all necessary for many daily activities. These visual skills allow you to visualize, use your peripheral vision, switch visual focus between target points at varying distances, sustain focus on a moving target, and more!

The 17 visual skills are essential for success in reading, writing, and sports performance. Reduced performance in any of these areas may indicate a problem with the visual skills. Vision is not only about how well you can see, it also involves 17 different visual skills that enable accurate, smooth, and precise eye movements for clear and comfortable vision— all necessary for many daily activities. These visual skills allow you to visualize, use your peripheral vision, switch visual focus between target points at varying distances, sustain focus on a moving target, and more!

The 17 visual skills are essential for success in reading, writing, and sports performance. Reduced performance in any of these areas may indicate a problem with the visual skills.</p>

</div>

</section>

<section>

<div class="container my-5">

<h3 style="color:

#323049;text-align: center;"><u>CLUB GALLERY</u></h3>

<!-- Gallery -->

<div class="row my-5">

<div class="col-lg-4 col-md-12 mb-4 mb-lg-0">

</div>

<div class="col-lg-4 mb-4 mb-lg-0">

</div>

<div class="col-lg-4 mb-4 mb-lg-0">

</div>
</div>
<!-- Gallery --></div>
</div>

</section>

 <!-- Footer -->
<footer class="page-footer font-small blue">

 <!-- Copyright -->
<div class="footer-copyright text-center py-3 text-light">© 2022 Copyright:
 Soccer
 Management System
</div>
 <!-- Copyright -->

</footer>
<!-- Footer -->
</section>
</body>
</html>
```

## COONNECT.PHP

```
<?php
$host = "localhost";
$users = "root";
$pass = "";
$database = "club";
$connection = mysqli_connect($host,$users,$pass,$database);
?>
```

# Screenshot

Server: MySQL-3306 » Database: club » Table: appointment

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra	Action
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	id			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT	<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	name	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	gender	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	email	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	place	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	phone			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	age	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	time	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>

Indexes

Action	Keyname	Type	Unique	Packed	Column	Cardinality	Collation	Null	Comment
<a href="#">Edit</a> <a href="#">Drop</a>	PRIMARY	BTREE	Yes	No	id	0	A	No	

Create an index on 1 column(s) after time [Go](#)

Server: MySQL-3306 » Database: club » Table: purchase

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra	Action
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	id			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT	<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	name			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	email			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	place			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	phone			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	item			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	color			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	size			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	country			No	None			<a href="#">Change</a> <a href="#">Drop</a> <a href="#">More</a>

Indexes

Action	Keyname	Type	Unique	Packed	Column	Cardinality	Collation	Null	Comment
<a href="#">Edit</a> <a href="#">Drop</a>	PRIMARY	BTREE	Yes	No	id	0	A	No	

Create an index on 1 column(s) after country [Go](#)

Partitions

phpMyAdmin

Current server: MySQL

Recent: Favorites

- New
- bus management
  - New
  - complaints
  - purchase
  - registration
  - stay
  - ticket
- club
  - New
  - appointment
  - event
  - purchase
- information\_schema
- mysql
- performance\_schema
- sys

Server: MySQL-3306 > Database: club > Table: event

Browse Structure SQL Search Insert Export Import Privileges Operations Triggers

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra	Action
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	id	int(11)		No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT	Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	name	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	email	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	phone	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	events	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	place	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	date	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	time	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	qty	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci	No	None			Change Drop More

Check all With selected: Browse Change Drop Primary Unique Index Fulltext Fulltext

Print Propose table structure Move columns Normalize

Add 1 column(s) after qty Go

Indexes

Action	Keyname	Type	Unique	Packed	Column	Cardinality	Collation	Null	Comment
<a href="#">Edit</a> <a href="#">Drop</a>	PRIMARY	BTREE	Yes	No	id	0	A	No	

Create an index on 1 columns Go

localhost / MySQL / club / event | Bootstrap (front-end framework) | SOCCER MANAGEMENT

localhost/project/registration.php

Apps YouTube Gmail Maps News Translate New Tab mmtuts |yiff.party Client Area - Freen... Adding Bootstrap... import.java.io... Reading list

**SOCCER MANAGEMENT** Home Registration Purchase Tickets Appointment Events **ADMIN**

Welcome To Soccer Management System

Name

Gender

Email address

Place

Phone

Age

localhost / MySQL / club / event | Bootstrap (front-end framework) | SOCCER MANAGEMENT | +

localhost/project/purchase.php

Apps YouTube Gmail Maps News Translate New Tab mmtuts | yiff.party Client Area - Freen... Adding Bootstrap [...] import.java.io; /... Reading list

**SOCCER MANAGEMENT** Home Registration Purchase Tickets Appointment Events **ADMIN**



**T-Shirts**  
Our club deliver high quality products to each customers

[Buy item](#)



**T-Shirts**  
Our club deliver high quality products to each customers.

[Buy item](#)



**T-Shirts**  
Our club deliver high quality products to each customers

[Buy item](#)

Enter details to conform your order

Name

localhost / MySQL / club / event | Bootstrap (front-end framework) | SOCCER MANAGEMENT | +

localhost/project/tickets.php

Apps YouTube Gmail Maps News Translate New Tab mmtuts | yiff.party Client Area - Freen... Adding Bootstrap [...] import.java.io; /... Reading list

**SOCCER MANAGEMENT** Home Registration Purchase Tickets Appointment Events **ADMIN**



**T-Series for men**  
Limited offer to buy upcoming matches ticket 50% off using promocode NEW.

[Buy Tickets](#)



**T-Series for female**  
Limited offer to buy upcoming matches ticket 50% off using promocode NEW.

[Buy Tickets](#)



**T-Series under 18**  
Limited offer to buy upcoming matches ticket 50% off using promocode NEW.

[Buy Tickets](#)

Enter details to conform your order

localhost/project/tickets.php Name

localhost / MySQL / club / event x Bootstrap (front-end framework) x Document x +

localhost/project/appointment.php

Apps YouTube Gmail Maps News Translate New Tab mmtuts | yiff.party Client Area - Freen... Adding Bootstrap [...] import.java.io; //...

**SOCCER MANAGEMENT** Home Registration Purchase Tickets Appointment Events ADMIN

**Enter your details to book an appointment**

Name

Gender

Email address

Place

Phone

Age

localhost/project/appointment.php

localhost / MySQL / club / event x Bootstrap (front-end framework) x SOCCER MANAGEMENT x +

localhost/project/event.php

Apps YouTube Gmail Maps News Translate New Tab mmtuts | yiff.party Client Area - Freen... Adding Bootstrap [...] import.java.io; //...

**SOCCER MANAGEMENT** Home Registration Purchase Tickets Appointment Events ADMIN



**T-Series santa party**  
 Limited offer to buy upcoming events ticket 50% off using promocode NEW.  
[Buy Tickets](#)



**T-Series award night**  
 Limited offer to buy upcoming events ticket 50% off using promocode NEW.  
[Buy Tickets](#)



**T-Series beach party**  
 Limited offer to buy upcoming events ticket 50% off using promocode NEW.  
[Buy Tickets](#)

**Enter details to conform your order**

Name

localhost/project/event.php

localhost / MySQL / club / event | Bootstrap (front-end framework) | Document

localhost/project/admin.php

Apps YouTube Gmail Maps News Translate New Tab mmtuts | yiff.party Client Area - Freen... Adding Bootstrap [...] import.java.io: //... Reading list

**SOCCER MANAGEMENT** Home Registration Purchase Tickets Appointment Events **ADMIN**

### TABLE DETAILS

Table Name	Operations
Registration	<a href="#">View</a>
Purchase	<a href="#">View</a>
Ticket	<a href="#">View</a>
Appointment	<a href="#">View</a>
Event	<a href="#">View</a>

## **CONCLUSION**

The project training undertaken by me at "Tribhuvan University" helped me in not only gaining practical experience but also to adapt the technical skill and procedures.

It is said that no system is perfect; every system has some limitations and flaws. Taking this into consideration, the project "Soccer Management" for "Database Management System" has been carried out successfully.

Thus, I confidently conclude that this was not only beneficial in its technical and educational aspect but also wins equality in building up my personality.

## References

1. Acharya, Kamal, *Attendance Management System Project* (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
2. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Food Order System* (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
3. Acharya, Kamal, *University management system project*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
4. Acharya, Kamal, *Online banking management system*. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
5. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Job Portal Management System* (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
6. Acharya, Kamal, *Employee leave management system*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
7. Acharya, Kamal, *Online electricity billing project report*. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
8. Acharya, Kamal, *POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
9. Acharya, Kamal, *Online job placement system project report*. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
10. Acharya, Kamal, *Software testing for project report*. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
11. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT*. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
12. Acharya, Kamal, *Burger ordering system project report*. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>
13. Acharya, Kamal, *Teachers Record Management System Project Report* (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>
14. Acharya, Kamal, *Dairy Management System Project Report* (December 20, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>
15. Acharya, Kamal, *Electrical Shop Management System Project* (December 10, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>

16. Acharya, Kamal, *Online book store management system project report*. (February 10, 2020). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>
17. Acharya, Kamal, *Paint shop management system project report*. (January 10, 2019). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>
18. Acharya, Kamal, *Supermarket billing system project report*. (August 10, 2021). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>
19. Acharya, Kamal, *Online taxi booking system project report*. (March 10, 2022). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>
20. Acharya, Kamal, *Online car servicing system project report*. (March 10, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>
21. Acharya, Kamal, *School management system project report*. (July 10, 2021). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>
22. Acharya, Kamal, *Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report* (March 21, 2021). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>
23. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report* (March 21, 2019). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>
24. Acharya, Kamal, *Fruit Shop Management System Project Report* (August 10, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>
25. Acharya, Kamal, *Hall Booking Management System Project Report* (December 21, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>
26. Acharya, Kamal, *Lundry Management System Project Report* (October 21, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>
27. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT* (September 25, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>
28. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT* (May 25, 2024). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>
29. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>
30. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2021). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>
31. Acharya, Kamal, *TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT* (August 21, 2023). Available at  
SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>

32. Acharya, Kamal, *Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report* (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>
33. Acharya, Kamal, *Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report* (April 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>
34. Acharya, Kamal, *Automobile management system project report* (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>
35. Acharya, Kamal, *College bus management system project report* (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>
36. Acharya, Kamal, *Courier management system project report* (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>
37. Acharya, Kamal, *Event management system project report* (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>
38. Acharya, Kamal, *Library management system project report II* (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>
39. Kamal Acharya. *Teacher record management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.46787329/v1>
40. Kamal Acharya. *POST OFFICE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.44494375/v1>
41. Kamal Acharya. *Fruit shop management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.42227675/v1>
42. Kamal Acharya. *Dairy management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261513.39402347/v1>
43. Kamal Acharya. *DATA COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER NETWORK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.37480177/v1>
44. Kamal Acharya. *School management system project report*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
45. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>
46. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
47. Kamal Acharya. *Web chatting application project report management system*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
48. Kamal Acharya. *RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>

49. Kamal Acharya. SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>
50. Kamal Acharya. SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. August 01, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.11210579/v1>
51. Kamal Acharya. Online music portal management system project report. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252488.89734698/v1>
52. Kamal Acharya. COLLEGE BUS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245277.70798942/v1>
53. Kamal Acharya. AUTOMOBILE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 31, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245276.67982593/v1>
54. Kamal Acharya. Ludo management system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243999.98091616/v1>
55. Kamal Acharya. Literature online quiz system project report. Authorea. July 31, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243825.53562953/v1>
56. Kamal Acharya. Avoid waste management system project. Authorea. July 29, 2024  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228528.85022205/v1>
57. Kamal Acharya. CHAT APPLICATION THROUGH CLIENT SERVER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT. Authorea. July 29, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228527.74316529/v1>
58. Kamal Acharya. Parking allotment system project report. Authorea. July 29, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172227078.89966943/v1>
59. Kamal Acharya. HEALTH INSURANCE CLAIM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM. Authorea. July 26, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172202020.06707762/v1>
60. Kamal Acharya. ONLINE TRAIN BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 22, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172167914.45160406/v1>
61. Kamal Acharya. COVID MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 16, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172116616.60220024/v1>
62. Kamal Acharya. COVID MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. Authorea. July 16, 2024.  
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172116616.60220024/v1>